

STRUCTURE–EFFICIENCY RELATIONSHIP OF PHENOTIAZINE DYES IN DYES-SENSITIZED SOLAR CELLS: A QUANTITATIVE STRUCTURE–PROPERTY RELATIONSHIP (QSPR) STUDY

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ABSTRACT. Dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) represent a promising third-generation photovoltaic technology in which the organic sensitizer plays a pivotal role in light harvesting and charge injection. In this work, a Quantitative Structure–Property Relationship (QSPR) approach was applied to a series of eleven phenothiazine-based organic dyes to predict their power conversion efficiency (PCE). Molecular geometries were optimized using DFT at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level of theory with Gaussian09, yielding frontier orbital energies (HOMO and LUMO) for all compounds. A set of 124 three-dimensional (3D) molecular descriptors were generated using MOE (version 2015) and processed through variance filtering and correlation analysis. The six most pertinent descriptors were chosen using a genetic algorithm (GA). Six linear QSPR models were developed and validated by leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO-CV). Model 3, built on three descriptors (b_1rotR, MNDO_LUMO, and Vsurf_DW13), emerged as the best model with $R^2_{cv} = 0.745$ and $RMSE_{cv} = 0.726$. External validation on three independent compounds confirmed the robustness of the model. These results highlight molecular flexibility, LUMO energy, and surface hydrophilicity as key structural determinants of PCE in phenothiazine-based DSSCs.

KEY WORDS: DSSCs, Phenothiazine, QSPR, DFT, Power Conversion Efficiency, Molecular Descriptors, Genetic Algorithm, MOE

INTRODUCTION

Recently, research into renewable photovoltaic technology has increased due to the persistent need for clean electricity and the rising global energy demand. Dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) have attracted worldwide attention since their first discovery by Grätzel in 1991, due to their promising conversion efficiency, ease of fabrication, and low manufacturing cost compared to conventional silicon-based devices [1].

Since it has a major impact on cell performance, the organic dye sensitizer is the most crucial part of DSSCs. A sensitizer needs to meet a number of crucial physicochemical conditions in order to work properly:

- Solar light is well absorbed throughout the visible spectrum.
- The dye is bound to the semiconductor surface (usually TiO₂) by at least one anchoring group.
- A HOMO energy level below the electrolyte redox potential to guarantee dye regeneration, and a LUMO energy level above the TiO₂ conduction band edge to guarantee effective electron injection from the excited dye into the conduction band.
- Minimization of unfavorable dye

aggregation on the semiconductor surface, which can be controlled through molecular design or use of co-adsorbents.

- Photostability, thermal stability, and electrochemical stability under operating conditions [1]. Among organic sensitizers, phenothiazine-based dyes have emerged as highly promising candidates owing to their characteristic donor– π –acceptor (D– π –A) architecture, strong electron-donating ability from the sulfur- and nitrogen-containing tricyclic core, wide structural tunability, eco-friendliness, and cost-effective synthesis compared to metal-complex dyes. Phenothiazine sensitizers have been extensively studied and optimized to capture more photons while retaining good charge recombination resistance [2].

Very recently, Quantitative Structure–Property Relationship (QSPR)[3] modeling has become an increasingly powerful tool, enabled by the growth of computing capabilities to rationalize and accelerate the design of more efficient sensitizers. QSPR models establish mathematical relationships between molecular descriptors and experimentally measured properties such as PCE. These models serve not only to predict properties of untested compounds, but also to prioritize synthesis efforts and provide mechanistic insight into structure–efficiency relationships. [4,5]

Prior to the calculation of molecular descriptors in QSPR studies, molecular structures must be properly prepared through geometry optimization to ensure reliable theoretical parameters. Density Functional Theory (DFT) has proven to be a powerful and reliable approach for obtaining optimized geometries and has been successfully applied in several theoretical investigations. [6,7]

In a previous work, we DFT calculations at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level to investigate metal-free organic dyes used in dye-sensitized solar cells DSSCs. Several conceptual DFT-derived indices were calculated and showed a good correlation with the experimental photovoltaic efficiencies of the dyes. [8]

In this work, we combined DFT quantum chemical calculations with QSPR modeling to elaborate predictive models for the PCE of phenothiazine-based DSSC sensitizers, using the MOE (Molecular Operating Environment) software[9,10]. The dataset was derived from the experimental work of Buene et al. [11], and six linear QSPR models were developed, internally and externally validated, to identify the best predictive model and interpret the key structural determinants of efficiency.

Therefore, the developed QSPR model represents a promising computational tool for the prediction and rational design of efficient organic dyes, which may significantly reduce experimental cost and time in the development of high-performance DSSCs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data set

The selection of the 11 compounds in this dataset (D1–D11, ranging from AFB-3 to AFB-29) was primarily based on the availability of complete experimental parameters in the literature, notably their power conversion efficiency (PCE) [11]. Detailed chemical properties and PCE values for these molecules are summarized in Table 1, while their corresponding chemical architectures and molecular structures are illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 1. Chemical properties of the organic dyes and the corresponding PCEs (data from Buene et al. [2]).

Compounds	Molecular Formula	MW (g/mol)	Donor Group	Acceptor	PCE (%)
D1:AFB-3	C ₃₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	560.71	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	4.37
D2:AFB-9	C ₃₃ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	566.73	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	5.82
D3:AFB-20	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	460.61	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	5.34
D4:AFB-22	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	454.59	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	4.06

D5:AFB-23	$C_{26}H_{24}N_2O_2S_2$	460.61	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	3.48
D6:AFB-24	$C_{28}H_{26}N_2O_2S$	454.59	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	2.27
D7:AFB-25	$C_{33}H_{30}N_2O_3S_2$	566.73	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	4.27
D8:AFB-26	$C_{35}H_{32}N_2O_3S$	560.71	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	3.43
D9:AFB-27	$C_{33}H_{30}N_2O_3S_2$	566.73	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	5.78
D10:AFB-28	$C_{35}H_{32}N_2O_3S$	560.71	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	4.67
D11:AFB-29	$C_{35}H_{32}N_2O_3S$	560.71	Phenothiazine	Cyanoacrylic	1.06

Figure 1. Molecular structures of the sensitizers investigated in this study. The molecules

enclosed in the rounded rectangle correspond to the external validation set.

Geometry optimization and electronic properties

The molecular structures of the organic metal-free dyes were initially modeled using HyperChem 8.0.10 software [12]. To obtain reliable starting conformations, a preliminary geometry pre-optimization was performed using the AMBER (Assisted Model Building with Energy Refinement) force field [13]. This force field was selected over MM+ due to its superior parametrization for conjugated systems and organic molecules with complex functional groups, which are typical in dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) [14]. Subsequently, full geometry optimizations and vibrational frequency calculations were carried out in the gas phase using the Gaussian 09 package [15]. These calculations were performed at the Density Functional Theory (DFT) level using the B3LYP hybrid functional combined with the 6-31G(d,p) basis set [16]. The B3LYP functional is widely recognized for its accuracy in describing the electronic properties of organic sensitizers [17]. The absence of imaginary frequencies was verified to ensure that all optimized structures correspond to true local minima on the potential energy surface.

For every sensitizer, the frontier molecular orbital energies, HOMO (Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital) and LUMO (Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbital), were obtained using DFT calculations. Understanding the light-harvesting capacity, the thermodynamics of electron injection into the TiO₂ conduction band, and dye renewal by the electrolyte all depend on these characteristics.

Table 2 and Figure 2 provide the frontier molecular orbital energies and the energy gaps for the 11 studied sensitizers. The examined dyes HOMO, LUMO and band gap energies levels improve their use as sensitizers for DSSCs: they demonstrate a significant ability to absorb visible light and efficiently transfer electrons between TiO₂ valence and conduction bands.

Table 2. Electronic parameters of dyes for DSSC analysis

Parameters	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	D9	D10	D11
E _{HOMO} (eV)	-5.36	-5.4	-5.54	-5.15	-5.57	-5.18	-5.42	-5.44	-5.43	-5.47	-5.41
E _{LUMO} (eV)	-2.76	-2.79	-2.81	-2.77	-2.89	-2.78	-2.87	-2.97	-2.79	-2.97	-2.91
E _g (eV)	2.6	2.61	2.72	2.38	2.68	2.4	2.55	2.47	2.64	2.5	2.51
E _{cb} TiO ₂	-4.00	-4.00	-4.00	-4.00	-4.00	-4.00	-4.00	-4.00	-4.00	-4.00	-4.00
E _{redox} I ⁻ /I ₃	-4.80	-4.80	-4.80	-4.80	-4.80	-4.80	-4.80	-4.80	-4.80	-4.80	-4.80

Figure 2. Frontier molecular orbital energy levels and HOMO-LUMO bandgap of all dyes calculated at B3LYP/ 6-31G (d, p) level, along with the energy of TiO₂ conduction band (blue dashed line) and the redox potential of I⁻/I₃⁻ electrolyte (green dashed line).red bars. Black and red bars represent HOMO and LUMO levels, respectively.

Frontier molecular orbital (FMO) analysis and energy level alignment

As shown in Table 2, the calculated HOMO energy levels of the 11 studied sensitizers range from -5.15 eV to -5.57 eV, while the LUMO levels vary between -2.76 eV and -2.97 eV, resulting in energy band gaps (E_g) within the 2.38–2.68 eV range. For an efficient photovoltaic process, the energy levels of the sensitizer must be precisely aligned with those of the semiconductor and the redox electrolyte [14]. Recent reviews emphasize that metal-free organic dyes with a D- π -A architecture are highly effective due to their high molar absorption coefficients and tunable energy levels, which are essential for optimizing intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) [18,19].

To ensure effective electron injection, the LUMO of the dye must be more negative (higher in energy) than the conduction band edge (E_{cb}) of the TiO₂ semiconductor [1]. Taking the E_{cb} of TiO₂ as -4.0 eV (vs. vacuum), all 11 sensitizers exhibit LUMO levels significantly above this threshold. This substantial energy offset (1.03 to 1.24 eV) provides a sufficient driving force (ΔG_{inject}) for rapid electron injection from the excited dye into the TiO₂ conduction band [20].

On the other hand, for efficient dye regeneration, the HOMO level must be deeper (more positive) than the redox potential of the I⁻/I₃⁻ electrolyte, typically situated at approximately -4.8 eV vs. vacuum [21]. The calculated HOMO values (-5.15 to -5.57 eV) confirm that all sensitizers possess a favorable potential gradient (0.35 to 0.77 eV). This ensures that the oxidized dye can be effectively reduced by iodide ions, thereby minimizing charge recombination at the photoanode interface [22,23]. Finally, the band gaps (2.38–2.68 eV) indicate that these organic molecules are well-suited for harvesting solar radiation in the visible region, which is critical for maximizing short-circuit current (J_{sc}) [24,25].

Figure 3 shows the spatial distribution of the frontier molecular orbitals (HOMO and LUMO) of the investigated dyes. As observed, the HOMO is predominantly localized on the donor unit, while the LUMO is mainly distributed over the π -conjugated bridge and acceptor moiety, suggesting an efficient intramolecular charge transfer (ICT), which is favorable for electron injection into TiO₂.

AFB-20 dye (D3)

AFB-22 dye (D4)

Dyes

AFB-23 dye (D5)

AFB-24 dye (D6)

AFB-25 dye (D7)

AFB-26 dye (D8)

AFB-27dye (D9)

AFB-28dye (D10)

Figure 3. Frontier molecular orbitals (HOMO and LUMO) of the studied dyes calculated at the B3LYP/6-31G (d,p) level.

Molecular descriptor calculation and preprocessing

Three-dimensional (3D) molecular descriptors were calculated using the QSPR module of the MOE software (version 2015), starting from the DFT-optimized geometries. A total of 124 i3D descriptors were initially computed, covering topological, electronic, geometric, and surface-based properties. These descriptors were preprocessed in two steps: (i) removal of near-constant descriptors using a variance threshold of 0.0001, and (ii) removal of highly correlated descriptors using a Pearson correlation coefficient cutoff of 0.99, retaining one representative per correlated cluster. [26]

Feature selection and QSPR model construction

The best collection of descriptors for QSPR modeling was found using a genetic algorithm (GA) built using MOE. The GA minimizes a fitness function based on cross-validated prediction error, exploring the descriptor space iteratively. This procedure led to the selection of six descriptors that best capture the structural determinants of PCE. Their identities and physicochemical significance are presented in Table 4. [27]

Table 3. Selected molecular descriptors and their physicochemical significance.

Descriptor	Physicochemical Significance
BCUT_SLOGP2	BCUT descriptor using atomic contribution to logP (Wildman & Crippen SlogP method) instead of partial charge.
b_1rotR	Fraction of rotatable single bonds: b_1rotN divided by b_heavy.
b_rotR	Fraction of rotatable bonds: b_rotN divided by b_heavy.
MNDO_LUMO	Energy (eV) of the Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbital calculated using the MNDO Hamiltonian [MOPAC].
PM3_LUMO	Energy (eV) of the Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbital calculated using the PM3 Hamiltonian [MOPAC].
Vsurf_DW13	Contact distances of Vsurf EWmin (hydrophilic/hydrophobic surface balance descriptor).

The individual linear correlation coefficients (R^2) between each selected descriptor and the experimental PCE are reported in Table 5. Among the six descriptors, Vsurf_DW13 exhibits the highest individual correlation with PCE ($R^2 = 0.639$), indicating that the polar surface balance of the sensitizer is the single most predictive structural feature. The remaining descriptors show moderate individual correlations (R^2 between 0.235 and 0.279), highlighting the need for a multivariate model to adequately capture PCE.

Table 4. Individual linear correlation coefficients (R^2) between each selected descriptor and experimental PCE.

Descriptor	Individual R ² with PCE
BCUT_SLOGP2	0.23518
b_1rotR	0.27894
b_rotR	0.27894
MNDO_LUMO	0.2478
PM3_LUMO	0.24711
Vsurf_DW13	0.63899

Six linear multivariate QSPR models were then constructed by MLR, each using a different combination of the selected descriptors. The stability and robustness of each model were assessed using R², RMSE, and Fisher F-criterion, with descriptor significance confirmed by Student t-test at the 95% confidence level.

Model validation

Internal validation was carried out using leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO-CV): each compound is iteratively excluded from the training set, the model is rebuilt on the remaining data, and the PCE of the excluded compound is predicted. This yields R²_{cv} and RMSE_{cv}, which measure the true generalization performance of the model. Acceptance criteria are: R²_{cv} ≥ 0.5 and RMSE_{cv} < 1.0.

Outlier detection was performed by computing standardized residuals: ZSCORE for the response variable (predicted PCE residuals) and XZSCORE for the descriptor space. Both quantities must remain below 2.5 in absolute value for all compounds; this confirms that all data points lie within the applicability domain of the model.

External validation was performed on three phenothiazine compounds not included in the training set, selected from a pool of 13 candidate molecules after preliminary testing. Their experimental PCE values were compared to the predictions of the best model (Model 3).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The theoretical calculations reported in this work were initially performed within the framework of a Master research project at the Higher School of Applied Sciences of Tlemcen (ESSAT), under the supervision of the authors. [28]

QSPR models and statistical performance

Six QSPR models were developed and their statistical performance is summarized in Table 5, which contains the model equations and cross-validated coefficients.

Table 5. QSPR model equations and cross-validated statistical indicators for the six models.

Model	Equation	RMSE (cv)	R ² (cv)
1	$PCE = -2.131455 - (7.21093 * vsurf_DW13) - (40.20253 * b_rotR) + (26.00520 * BCUT_SLOGP_2)$	0.9701	0.5452
2	$PCE = -55.60109 + (308.81014 * b_1rotR) - (21.22701 * b_rotR) - (7.47817 * vsurf_DW13)$	0.74876	0.734
3	$PCE = -60.44495 + (309.50289 * b_1rotR) + (0.62626 * MNDO_LUMO) - (7.45951 * vsurf_DW13)$	0.72634	0.7455
4	$PCE = -10.87321 + (25.44033 * BCUT_SLOGP_2) + (1.09216 * MNDO_LUMO) - (7.09075 * vsurf_DW13)$	1.04578	0.478
5	$PCE = -63.21981 - (7.34896 * BCUT_SLOGP_2) + (344.32020 * b_1rotR) - (7.01548 * vsurf_DW13)$	0.73818	0.743

6	$PCE = -55.6537 + (286.56470 * b_1rotR) + (0.22245 * PM3_LUMO) - (7.18287 * vsurf_DW13)$	0.77232	0.7159
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As shown in Table 6, five of the six models achieve acceptable internal validation performance ($R^2_{cv} > 0.5$ and $RMSE_{cv} < 1.0$), and all standardized residuals (ZSCORE and XZSCORE) are below 2.5 for all training compounds, confirming the absence of outliers and the validity of the applicability domain. Only Model 4 is considered poor, with $RMSE = 1.046$ and R^2_{cv} below the acceptance threshold, and was therefore discarded.

Model 3 was identified as the best model in this study, with the highest cross-validated correlation coefficient ($R^2_{cv} = 0.745$) and the lowest cross-validated error ($RMSE_{cv} = 0.726$). The corresponding correlation plots for all six models are provided in Figures 4.

Figures 4. Correlation between experimental and predicted PCE values for Models 1–6, with Model3 demonstrating the highest predictive accuracy.

Analysis of the best model (Model 3)

Model 3 incorporates three descriptors: b_{1rotR} , MNDO_LUMO, and V_{surf_DW13} . Each of these descriptors captures a distinct and complementary physicochemical dimension governing DSSC efficiency, as detailed below.

b_{1rotR} is a topological descriptor representing the fraction of rotatable single bonds relative to the total number of heavy atom bonds. In D- π -A sensitizers, a high degree of conformational flexibility (large b_{1rotR}) can disrupt the coplanarity of the π -conjugated bridge, reducing the efficiency of intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) from the phenothiazine donor to the anchoring acceptor group. Rigid, planar molecular architectures are therefore associated with more effective π -delocalization and higher PCE.

MNDO_LUMO is the LUMO energy computed at the MNDO semi-empirical level (MOPAC). As established by the DFT results (Tables 2 and 3), the LUMO energy is a critical determinant of electron injection efficiency: a lower (more negative) LUMO energy indicates a stronger driving force for electron injection from the excited sensitizer into the TiO₂ conduction band. This descriptor thus provides a computationally efficient proxy for the quantum-chemical electron-accepting properties of the dye.

V_{surf_DW13} is a surface-based descriptor related to the hydrophilic/hydrophobic balance of the molecular surface (contact distances of V_{surf} EWmin). This descriptor is highly relevant to the anchoring of the sensitizer on TiO₂: a balanced polar surface facilitates strong carboxylate-TiO₂ binding while limiting competitive water adsorption and dye desorption. The high individual R^2 of this descriptor (0.639, Table 5) confirms it as the most important single predictor of PCE in this dataset.

Together, these three descriptors encode the conformational rigidity, electron injection driving force, and surface anchoring capacity of the sensitizer — three key mechanistic factors governing DSSCs efficiency. Their combination in Model 3 yields a physically meaningful and statistically robust predictive equation.

External validation

To evaluate the accurate predictive power of Model 3, it was applied to three phenothiazine compounds not included in the training set [29-31] used as test set, selected after preliminary screening from a pool of 13 candidate molecules. The obtained results show that the same trend for the experimental values is obtained, indeed for D12 the (EXP PCE%=7.0000 and PRED=6.7015)<D13 (EXP PCE%=7.6100; PRED=7.7304) < D15 (EXP PCE%=8.0000; PRED=9.5746).

Figure 5. Correlation between QSPR-predicted and experimental PCE values for the external validation set.

The predicted PCE values are in good agreement with the experimental data. These results confirm the robustness and generalization capability of Model 3 beyond the training set. The correlation plot (Figure 5) further illustrates the predictive accuracy of the model for independent compounds, validating its applicability for prospective prediction of PCE in novel phenothiazine-based sensitizers.

CONCLUSION

In this work, QSPR models were successfully developed and validated for the prediction of the power conversion efficiency (PCE) of phenothiazine-based organic dye sensitizers in DSSCs. DFT calculations at the B3LYP/6-31G(d) level provided frontier orbital energies (HOMO and LUMO) for all compounds, confirming their suitability as DSSC sensitizers from a thermodynamic standpoint. A pool of 124 three-dimensional molecular descriptors was generated using MOE, preprocessed statistically, and reduced to six informative descriptors by a genetic algorithm: BCUT_SLOGP2, b_1rotR, b_rotR, MNDO_LUMO, PM3_LUMO, and Vsurf_DW13.

Six linear QSPR models were built and evaluated. Model 3, incorporating b_1rotR, MNDO_LUMO, and Vsurf_DW13, was identified as the best model with a cross-validated correlation coefficient $R^2_{cv} = 0.745$ and $RMSE_{cv} = 0.726$. All standardized residuals (ZSCORE and XZSCORE) remained below 2.5, confirming the absence of outliers and the validity of the applicability domain. External validation on three independent compounds confirmed the predictive robustness of the model.

The structural interpretation of Model 3 reveals that high PCE in phenothiazine sensitizers is favored by: (i) rigid molecular architectures that preserve π -conjugation and intramolecular charge transfer (low b_1rotR); (ii) low LUMO energies that provide a strong thermodynamic driving force for electron injection into TiO₂ (MNDO_LUMO); and (iii) a balanced hydrophilic/hydrophobic surface that promotes effective anchoring on the semiconductor (Vsurf_DW13).

The developed QSPR model provides a reliable and interpretable computational tool for the virtual screening and rational design of new phenothiazine-based sensitizers, reducing the need for costly experimental synthesis and testing. Future work will focus on expanding the dataset, exploring nonlinear machine learning methods, and incorporating TD-DFT spectral descriptors to further improve predictive performance.

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